

Influence of porous structure on the ionic conductivity of nano ZnO incorporated PVC-PEG polymer nanocomposite electrolytes

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Abstract : Polymer electrolyte membrane comprising poly(vinyl chloride) PVC and poly(ethylene glycol) PEG blend as matrix, lithium per chloride (LiClO_4) as dopant salt and propylene carbonate (PC) as plasticizer was prepared by solution casting method. The nanosized ZnO particles were synthesized through novel solid state milling and calcination of zinc acetate and citric acid powders. The wt% of synthesized particles were systematically varied and incorporated as filler in PVC-PEG polymer matrix to study its influence on the conductivity of polymer electrolytes. The films were subjected to XRD and AC impedance analysis in the frequency range 50–100 KHz at room temperature. The analysis shows strong influence of filler particles on the ionic conductivity of the membranes. The conductivity profile features two maxima occurring at 0.5 wt% and at 4 wt% of filler. The 4 wt% filler added membrane exhibits 10 times enhancement in the conductivity value than the filler free electrolyte membrane. The enhancement in the conductivity was examined through surface morphological (SEM) studies.

Keywords : Polymer electrolytes, phase separation, ionic conductivity, ZnO filler, SEM analysis.

Introduction

The porous structured polymer membranes are widely used in micro-filtration, protein adsorption, water treatment, proton and ionic conductivity¹ and controlled release of drugs. Polymer electrolyte film has the transport properties comparable to those of liquid electrolytes. The advantages of these electrolytes are no internal shorting and no leakage of electrolytes. To enhance the ionic conductivity many attempts have been carried out such as blending², cross-linking³, and addition of nano/micro fillers⁴. There are several features such as crystallinity, chain structure, flexibility, porosity, pore size contribute to the mobility of charge carriers. Much research has been carried out to increase the liquid electrolyte content in the polymer matrix by controlling the components and morphology as the ionic conductivity of the solid polymer electrolyte increases with increasing amount of the liquid electrolyte absorbed in the polymer matrix⁵. The pore structure of the polymer membrane is one of the key component and especially important for the ionic conductivity. A high porosity leads to a high conductivity but the mechanical stability or free standing nature of the

polymer electrolytes will simultaneously trade off⁶. To overcome this problem we have chosen PVC as polymer host which exhibits itself in a phase-separated morphology, because of its poor solubility in the liquid electrolyte that provides a rigid structure to the electrolyte films⁷. The preference of PVC is attributed to the presence of lone pair of electrons at the chlorine atom where inorganic salts can be solvated. The dipole-dipole interaction between the hydrogen and chlorine atoms may stiffen the polymer backbone and may render the PVC-salt complexation difficult. This can be minimized by blending with another polymer. We have prepared phase-separated polymer electrolyte based on blend of PVC and PEG, as the latter can act as an additional plasticizer. The lower viscosity of the plasticizer decreases the T_g and increases the amorphous content, where as higher dielectric constant of the plasticizer aids better ionic dissociation⁸. The decrease in T_g increases the local chain flexibility which is coupled to the ionic mobility. We have synthesized PVC-PEG blend electrolyte with propylene carbonate as the plasticizer, LiClO_4 as salt and nano ZnO as filler. The (PVC : ZnO) weight ratio is systematically varied

without varying other constituents to study its influence on the conductivity of the membranes. The preliminary results of our study are reported earlier⁹ here an attempt has been made to investigate the variation of conductivity through morphological studies.

Experimental

Zinc acetate dihydrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and citric acid ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_7$) in powder form (AR grade) were weighed separately (molar ratio of 1 : 1), mixed together and ground for 2 h at room temperature. The milled powders were calcinated in air at 400 °C to obtain ZnO nano particles¹⁰. These synthesized ZnO particles in different wt% were used as filler. Poly vinyl chloride (PVC) of average molecular weight 60,000 was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used after drying under vacuum at 60 °C for 24 h. Poly ethylene glycol (PEG) (mol. wt. = 200) was procured from CDH, India. Propylene carbonate was purchased from Merck used without any purification and LiClO_4 from Sigma-Aldrich, dried by annealing under vacuum at 120 °C for 24 h. Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was procured from Merck and used as solvent. The appropriate quantity of PVC, PEG and LiClO_4 were dissolved in THF to form homogeneous viscous solution. Then predetermined ZnO (wt%) particles were added and stirred continuously for a period of 10–12 h. The viscous slurry was poured into glass petri dishes and left to dry at room temperature to form a film. The films were further dried in a temperature-controlled oven at 50 °C for 24 h. Finally, mechanically stable, free standing thin films were obtained and kept in desiccator for further analysis.

Results and discussion

XRD analysis :

The ionic mobility in a polymer electrolyte is facilitated by the amorphous nature of the polymer. The crystalline structure of the resultant electrolyte films was investigated using JEOL, JDX 8030 X-ray diffractometer at room temperature. XRD patterns of pure PVC, PEG, and LiClO_4 are shown in Fig. 1(a-c). The broad peak corresponding to PVC depicts the amorphous nature of the polymer. The two prominent peaks of PEG at $2\theta = 19.2^\circ$ and 23.4° show the crystalline nature of polymer. The diffraction pattern of synthesized ZnO particles after

calcinated at 400 °C for period of 2 h is indicated in Fig. 1(d). The diffraction peaks corresponding to the hexagonal ZnO (JCPDS card no. 36-1451) are observed. The average crystallite size of samples was determined by Debye Scherrer's formula : $D = k\lambda/\beta \cos \theta$, where k is a constant, λ the X-ray wavelength (0.154095 nm), β full wavelength at half maximum and θ is half diffraction angle. The average particle size determined using the above formula is 20 nm. The peaks pertaining to the salt are absent in the composite electrolyte film with 0 wt%, 1 wt% and 4 wt% of filler Fig. 1(e-g). This shows that the inorganic salt is solvated by the host polymer system. The ZnO peaks are present in the polymer complex with very low intensity indicating the interaction between polymer, salt and ZnO. Similar observation was found in TiO_2 incorporated PVC-PEG composite polymer electrolytes¹¹.

Conductivity analysis :

The ionic conductivity of a polymer electrolyte is determined by the concentration of the conducting species and their mobility. In the present work electrolyte mem-

Fig. 1. XRD spectra of (a) PVC, (b) PEG, (c) LiClO_4 , (d) ZnO and the complexes (PVC : ZnO) wt%, (e) (25 : 0), (f) (24 : 1), (g) (21 : 4).

brane were prepared with different wt% of (PVC : ZnO) = (25 : 0), (24.5 : 0.5), (24 : 1), (23 : 2), (21 : 4) and (19 : 6). To calculate the conductivity value of the polymer electrolytes impedance spectroscopy was performed using a computer controlled micro Auto lab in the frequency range 50 Hz–100 KHz at room temperature. The samples were cut into proper sizes and kept between indigenously designed two stainless steel electrodes with a spring system to exert a little pressure for better contact. The conductivity (σ) value was determined using the relation $\sigma = t/R_b A$, where, t is the thickness of the electrolyte, A , the electrode contact area and R_b is the bulk resistance obtained from the plots of real impedance (Z_r) versus imaginary impedance (Z_i). Fig. 2 shows the dependence of ionic conductivity on the nano ZnO concentration. The magnitude of the conductivity varies nonlinearly with filler concentration. The maximum conductivity of 6.052×10^{-6} S/cm at room temperature was observed for the system with composition (PVC : ZnO) : PEG : PC : LiClO₄ = (21 : 4) : 15 : 50 : 10. The conductivity variation further features two maxima one occurring at 0.5 wt% and at 4 wt% of ZnO filler. This type of conductivity variation in composite electrolyte systems is reported in earlier works¹². The first conductivity maximum is attributed to the creation of free ions as a result of addition of filler into the electrolytes. The decrease in the conductivity beyond the first maximum is related with the formation of ion pairs and larger-sized ion clusters due to re-association of freed ions when filler is added. The second maximum in the conductivity value is associated to the composite effect and explained on the basis of the formation of a conducting interfacial space-charge double-layer between the nano-sized ZnO particles and polymer gel electrolytes¹³. The decrease in conduc-

Fig. 2. Variation of conductivity with filler concentration.

tivity after the second conductivity maximum is related to the blocking effect of excess filler particles, which restricts the motion of mobile ions¹⁴. An approximate 10 times enhancement in ionic conductivity value is observed in the electrolyte with dispersion of 4 wt% ZnO filler with a meager improvement in the mechanical strength.

SEM analysis :

The surface morphology of the films was investigated by JEOL, JSM-840A Scanning electron microscope. Fig. 3(a-c) shows the morphology of the film without filler, with 1 wt% of filler and 4 wt% of filler. The plasticizer is absorbed into the film due to the miscibility with PEG and PVC is coagulated due to its immiscibility with the plasticizer. The liquid electrolyte is extracted from the polymer membrane by freeze-drying before SEM measurement. The presence of pores indicates the occurrence of phase-separation in the polymer electrolytes. The pores are the domains where liquid electrolyte has been absorbed. The morphology of the phase separation is determined when the PVC-rich phase is coagulated and im-

Fig. 3. SEM images of the electrolyte membranes with (PVC : ZnO) : (a) (25 : 0), (b) (24 : 1) and (c) (21 : 4).

mobilized. The PVC rich phase gives the better mechanical support to the film and the plasticizer rich phase interconnected with each other provide a path for ionic transport.

The film without filler shows the well defined rigid network structure that depicts the dominance of PVC. The film with 1 wt% of filler disrupts the network structure but does not increase the porosity of the membrane. Hence the conductivity value is lower for this film. But the film with 4 wt% of filler decreases the rigidity of the network and increases the porosity in the membrane which aids in better mobility of freed ions. It has been suggested that the conduction in polymer electrolytes takes place through two distinct methods, due to the charge migration of ions between the coordinate sites of the host polymer and due to polymer chain segmental motion¹⁵. It is evident from the morphology of films with filler that the interaction of ZnO filler with the polymer host reduces the rigid structure and favors segmental motion which in turn enhances the conductivity.

Conclusion

ZnO nanoparticles were synthesized through thermal treatment of solid state milling of precursors, zinc acetate and citric acid powders. The synthesized nanoparticles were incorporated in different wt% as filler in the PVC-PEG blend electrolyte system. The conductivity analysis reveals the strong influence of filler particles on the con-

ductivity value of the films. The variation in the conductivity value of the membranes was examined through its morphological features.

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